

**READING, LISTENING, WRITING AND ADVANTAGES OF
SPEAKING**

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Abstract: In this article, the advantages of reading, listening, writing and speaking in learning foreign languages, as well as the fact that they develop students' cognitive activity, arouse interest in learning a foreign language and form communicative competence, were considered.

Key words: reading, speaking, cognitive activity, listening, writing, interest in learning, communicative competence.

Introduction.

The main goal of teaching "English language" is the formation of communicative competence, which includes several components:

- communication skills in speaking, listening, reading and writing;
- language knowledge and skills on this language building material to create and recognize information;
- Linguistic and regional knowledge to ensure the socio-cultural basis, without which it is impossible to form communicative competence.

Students learn English as a means of communication and must be able to use it in oral and written forms. In order for English to become an interpersonal and international communication tool, it is very important to master all forms of communication and all speech functions. Students should master the four types of speech activities: reading, listening, writing and speaking, and should not forget about the advantages of the three aspects of language related to them - vocabulary, phonetics and grammar.

Let's take a closer look at the advantages of reading, listening, writing and speaking in learning English:

Listening is a receptive type of speech activity related to the perception and understanding of the spoken message. When the teacher himself chooses the material he uses in his oral speech in the lesson, he should take into account the goals he sets for himself: first, to develop students' ability to listen and understand foreign speech; and secondly, the well-known expansion of students' passive vocabulary during the listening process and the development of their expectations from the context.

When using this or that form or phrase, the teacher must take all measures to make it correctly understood by the students. To achieve this, remember the following: using this or that English phrase, the teacher must follow the same form in subsequent lessons, and not replace it with an Uzbek equivalent or another similar phrase in English. The teacher must ensure that the students understand not only the general meaning of the expression he used, but also the individual parts.

Students' correct understanding of the teacher's speech should be systematically checked. Each new expression should be repeated many times by the teacher not only in the first lesson, but also in subsequent lessons.

The goals of listening training can be defined as follows: development of certain speech skills; teaching the ability to communicate, developing the necessary skills; memorization of speech material; teach students to understand the meaning of the sentence; teach students to distinguish the main thing in the flow of information; develop auditory memory and auditory response. When working with audio materials, it forms students' ability to work on several speaking skills at the same time.

Speaking is a productive type of speech activity, through which (verbal) communication is carried out. The content of speech is the expression of thought in oral form. Speech is based on pronunciation, lexical and grammatical skills. The goal of teaching speech in the English language class is to form speech skills that will allow the student to use them in extracurricular speech practice at the level of everyday communication generally accepted.

The realization of this goal is related to the formation of the following communication skills in students:

a) understand and create statements in English in accordance with the specific situation of communication, speech task and communicative intention;

b) perform their verbal and non-verbal behavior taking into account the rules of communication and the national-cultural characteristics of the country of the language being studied;

c) use reasonable methods of mastering the English language, improving it independently.

The most important way of speaking is communicative (oral) speech. The communicative situation as a method of teaching speaking in a foreign language consists of four factors:

1) the conditions of reality in which communication is carried out;

2) relations between official and informal communication representatives;

3) speech (speech) motivation;

4) implementation of the act of communication itself, which creates a new situation, motivation to speak.

The term typical communicative situation is understood as a real communication model, in which the speech behavior of interlocutors is carried out in their typical social and communicative roles.

Main body

Examples of a simple communicative (speech) situation: a conversation between a buyer and a seller, a theater cashier with an audience, a teacher with a student, etc. Another important component of the method of teaching speaking is the type of

communication. There are 3 types of communication: individual, group and public: In individual communication, two people participate. It is characterized by speed and reliability. Here, communication partners are equal in the share of participation in the "product" of the common speech. In group communication, several people participate in one communication process (conversation with friends, training, meeting). Mass communication is carried out with a relatively large number of individuals. Therefore, the communicative roles of participants in public communication are usually predetermined: speakers and listeners (see meetings, rallies, debates, etc.).

Speech (speech) is manifested in monologic and dialogic forms. When teaching dialogue, it is necessary to distinguish between different forms of dialogue and forms of working with them: dialogue-conversation, dialogue-scene, conversation between students and the teacher, pair and group forms. The monologue is characterized by expansion, coherence, consistency, reasonableness, semantic completeness, the presence of common constructions, and grammatical formality. The main difficulties in teaching speaking (speech) should include motivational problems, for example: students are shy to speak foreign languages, they are afraid to make mistakes, to be criticized; students do not have enough language and speech tools to solve the task; students, for one reason or another, do not participate in the collective discussion of the subject of the lesson. Based on the listed problems in teaching speech, a goal appears - to eliminate these problems, if possible. It is impossible to learn to speak without building simple dialogues on a certain topic, without getting into real situations. An interactive approach to teaching involves direct involvement of students in discussions, debates, discussion of problems, and therefore dialogue. Also, to form students' common language, intellectual, cognitive abilities, mental processes that are the basis of mastering communication in a foreign language, as well as students' feelings, emotions, readiness for communication, various types of communication culture is important. team interaction.

Reading is a receptive type of speech activity related to the perception and understanding of written text. In order to read and understand a foreign text, it is assumed that it has a set of phonetic, lexical and grammatical informative features that make the

recognition process instantaneous. In the process of reading, the processes of perception and understanding are simultaneously and closely related to each other

although the skills that ensure its process are conditionally divided into two groups: related to the "technical" side of reading (perception of graphic symbols and their connection with certain meanings and providing semantic processing of what is perceived - establishing semantic connections between language units of different levels, and thus the content of the text, the author's intention, etc.

In teaching reading at the initial stage, it is important to teach the student to read correctly, that is, to sound graphemes, to extract meaning, that is, to understand, evaluate, and use text information. These skills depend on how fast the child learns. Through the reading technique, we understand not only the quick and clear interrelationship of sound and letter, but also the connection of the sound-letter connection with the semantic meaning of what the child is reading. It is the high level of mastering the reading technique that allows the result of the reading process itself - to get quick and quality information.

Pedagogical requirements can be formulated when organizing the process of learning to read in a foreign language.

1. Practical orientation of the educational process: formulation of specific communicatively motivated tasks and questions aimed at solving practical problems that allow not only to acquire new knowledge and skills, but also to understand the content and meaning of what is being studied; in the system of teaching the technique of reading in a foreign language, mandatory separation of the loud stage of reading, articulation and intonation, phonetically correct speech and "inner hearing" skills will be strengthened.

2. Differentiated approach to education: taking into account the young psychological characteristics of students, their individual ways of cognitive activity in conveying new knowledge and forming skills and competencies; the use of analytical and synthetic exercises, tasks that differ in complexity depending on the individual

abilities of students; choosing adequate methods of work on reading aloud and self-teaching.

3. A complex and functional approach to education: building learning to read based on oral expectations, i.e. children read texts containing language material they have already learned orally; at the alphabet stage, mastering new letters, letter combinations, reading rules is carried out in accordance with the sequence of introduction of new lexical units and speech samples in oral speech.

4. Taking into account the specific characteristics of the mother tongue: use of positive transfer of reading skills formed or already formed in the mother tongue of students;

5. A comprehensive approach to the formation of motivation: in the lesson, more attention is paid to performing game tasks, acting in problematic situations of a communicative nature; the use of various types of visualizations that stimulate the understanding of new material, the creation of associative connections, supports that help to better master the rules of reading, graphic images of words, intonation patterns of phrases.

Result and discussion

According to the level of penetration into the content of the text and depending on the communicative needs, there is sight reading, search (see and search), access and learning. Reading reading is characterized by a correct and complete understanding of the content of the text, retelling of the received information, repetition in the synopsis, etc.

Reading is one of the most important types of communicative and cognitive activity of students. This activity is aimed at obtaining information from a written fixed text. Reading performs various functions: it serves for practical mastering of foreign languages, a means of learning language and culture, a means of information and educational activities, and a means of self-education.

Writing is an effective type of speech activity that provides the expression of thought in graphic form. In the methodology of teaching a foreign language, written and written speech is both a means and a goal of teaching a foreign language. Writing is a technical component of written speech. Written speech, together with speech, is a productive type of speech activity, which is expressed in the designation of some content through graphic symbols.

Writing is closely related to reading. their system has one graphical language system. When writing with graphic symbols, thought is encoded, while reading graphic symbols are decoded. If you correctly define the goals of writing and teaching writing, take into account the role of writing in the development of other skills, use fully appropriate exercise goals, perform them at a certain stage of learning, speaking will gradually become richer and more logical.

Writing helps develop grammatical skills when given basic copywriting tasks or tasks that require creativity, all of which are prerequisites for memorization. It is very difficult for students without written work to memorize lexical and grammatical material.

Tasks for teaching written speech. To form students' competences and skills: appropriate to the language models being studied in the written statement

use the following sentences; construction of language models according to lexical, spelling and grammatical standards; use a set of speech clichés and formulas characteristic of a certain form of written communication; giving openness, accuracy and precision to the statement, using the methods of linguistic and semantic compression of the text, presenting the written statement with logical consistency.

Writing can become an effective teaching tool only when students have reached a certain level of spelling skills and competence.

At the middle stage of education, the most complex type of speech communication is used, for example, thinking that requires students to have knowledge, a wide vocabulary and phrases that help them express their thoughts in writing.

The tasks to be solved in the teaching of written speech are the formation of the necessary graphic automatisms, speech thinking skills and the ability to formulate thoughts in accordance with the written style in students, to expand their worldview and knowledge, and to acquire cultural and intellectual preparation for creation. the content of the written work of speech, the formation of real ideas about the content of the topic, the style of speech and the graphic form of the written text. Written speech allows you to save linguistic and factual knowledge, serves as a reliable tool for thinking, encourages speaking, listening and reading in a foreign language.

Conclusion.

Written speech is considered as a creative communication skill and is understood as the ability to express one's thoughts in writing. For this, it is necessary to have the skills of spelling and calligraphy, the ability to organize and organize a written speech composed in internal speech, as well as the ability to choose adequate lexical and grammatical units. Recently, writing is seen as an aid in improving the effectiveness of foreign language teaching. In terms of modern means of communication such as e-mail, the Internet, etc., it is impossible not to consider the practical importance of written speech communication. In the modern world, the role of written communication is extremely high. But it is necessary to distinguish written activity and written speech. The activity of written speech is the purposeful and creative execution of thought in the written word, and written speech is the method of forming and forming thought in the signs of written language.

Effective writing is still under-taught in foreign language classes. Students' written skills often lag far behind the level of learning in other types of speaking activities. The letter is characterized by a three-part structure: stimulating-motivational, analytical-synthetic and executive.

The purpose of teaching written speech is to develop students' written communicative competence, which includes the acquisition of written signs, the content and form of written speech work. The tasks to be solved in teaching written speech are related to creating conditions for mastering the content of teaching written speech. Therefore, teaching writing is inextricably linked with teaching other types of speech

activity with speech and reading. Written speech allows you to save linguistic and factual knowledge, serves as a reliable tool for thinking, encourages speaking, listening and reading in a foreign language.

Reasonably used writing in learning a foreign language, due to its close connection with all types of speech activity, helps the student to master the material, to accumulate knowledge about the language and through the language.

Thus, when speaking, students should be able to convey information or explain, approve or condemn, convince, prove. Writing requires the ability of students to quickly correct their own and others' thoughts; writing from reading, processing material; writing an outline or abstract of a speech. In reading, the ability of students to quickly read newspaper and magazine articles and literary works of moderate complexity is important. Listening requires the ability to understand speech at a normal pace in live communication, as well as the meaning of television / radio programs.

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